

Synthesis of Dibenzo [b, h] [1, 6] Naphthyridine Derivatives : II

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Condensation of 4-hydroxy-7,10-dichlorodibenzo [b, h] [1, 6] naphthyridine with 5-diethylamino-2-aminopentane and 4-amino-2-diethylaminomethylphenol furnished 4-hydroxy-7-(4-diethylamino-1-methylbutylamino)-10-chlorodibenzo [b, h] [1, 6] naphthyridine and the corresponding 7-(4-hydroxy 3-diethylaminomethyl anilino) derivative respectively. Amino substituents underwent ready displacement in aqueous solution of their hydrochlorides and produced the 7-hydroxy derivative. Attempted Mannich reaction on 4,7-dihydroxy-10-chlorodibenzo [b, h] [1, 6] naphthyridine resulted in the recovery of the unchanged material. Attempts to iodochlorinate the amino compounds at low temperature also failed.

In part I of the series¹ we described the preparation of 4-hydroxy-7,10-dichlorodibenzo [b, h] [1, 6] naphthyridine and related compounds. The objective was to prepare compounds (I) which would contain both the units of a 4-aminoquinoline and halogenated oxyquinoline and thus might exhibit activity against both intestinal and extraintestinal amoebiasis.

Condensation of 2-amino-5-diethylaminopentane (Noval diamine) with 4-hydroxy 7,10-dichlorodibenzo [b, h] [1, 6] naphthyridine (II) was carried out in phenol, essentially according to Kermack and Storey². The resulting base, 4-hydroxy-7-(4-diethylamino-1-methylbutylamino)-10-chlorodibenzo [b, h] [1, 6] naphthyridine (IIIa) was isolated as the hydrochloride. Attempted crystallisation of the hydrochloride from ethanol surprisingly gave 4,7-dihydroxy-10-chlorodibenzo [b, h] [1, 6] naphthyridine (IV). Evidently the displacement of the basic chain occurred. An aqueous solution of the hydrochloride on keeping at room temperature also behaved likewise. The hydrolysis occurred, though slowly, on keeping the aqueous solution even in the refrigerator ($\sim 5^\circ$).

1. A. K. Sen and Prabal Sengupta, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 441.
2. W. O. Kermack and N. E. Storey, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 1389,

Somewhat similar behaviour, though in a much reduced scale, is also exhibited by quinacrine (atabrine) hydrochloride³.

Suitable substituents, *alpha* or *gamma* to nitrogen in nitrogenous heteroaromatic compounds, are generally susceptible to displacement by nucleophilic reagents. This allows the intermediate activated complex in such displacements to assume structures in which nitrogen atom(s) assumes the negative charge. The difference in energy of activation may account for their relative reactivities. Acid acts as a strong catalyst for such reactions, for, in the form of salts, the various resonance forms favourable to nucleophilic attack are much more readily assumed. It would thus account that 7-position of dibenzo [*b*, *h*] [1, 6] naphthyridine is much more activated than the corresponding position of the acridine series:

3. F. Mietzsch, H. Mauss and G. Hecht, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1937, 457.

In our objective to place the "o-cresol unit of amodiaquine" at 7-position of the tetracyclic ring, we wanted to ascertain the acid stability of the 7-anilino compounds at the outset. Thus condensation of *p*-anisidine and *p*-aminophenol with 4-hydroxy-7,10-dichloro dibenzo $[b, h]$ [1, 6] naphthyridine were effected smoothly in toluene solution to furnish 4-hydroxy-7-(4-methoxyanilino)-10-chlorodibenzo $[b, h]$ [1, 6] naphthyridine (IIIb) and the corresponding 7-(4-hydroxyanilino) derivative (IIIc) respectively. The hydrolytic behaviour was similar to that described above. 4-Amino-2-diethylaminomethylphenol⁴ was condensed with 4-hydroxy-7,10-dichlorodibenzo $[b, h]$ [1, 6] naphthyridine in toluene. The hydrochloride which separated from toluene was basified with a slight excess of ammonia and rapidly extracted out with chloroform; evaporation of the solvent left the free base, 4-hydroxy 7-(4-hydroxy-3-diethylaminomethylanilino)-10-chlorodibenzo $[b, h]$ [1,6] naphthyridine (IIIId). This compound is likewise susceptible to hydrolysis by acids. Attempted Mannich reaction on 4-hydroxy-7-(4-hydroxyanilino)-10-chlorodibenzo $[b, h]$ [1, 6] naphthyridine failed. It is of interest to note that the presence of 4-hydroxy group in the dibenzonaphthyridine ring is unable to induce a Mannich reaction to occur at the vulnerable 3-position. Thus attempted Mannich condensation of 4,7-dihydroxy-10-chlorodibenzo $[b, h]$ [1, 6] naphthyridine (IV) always led to the recovery of the unchanged material.

Our primary objective to prepare 1,10-dichloro-3-iodo-4-hydroxy-7-(4-diethylamino-1-methylbutylamino) dibenzo $[b, h]$ [1, 6] naphthyridine remains to be done. Iodochlorination of 8-hydroxyquinoline is readily achieved by treatment of an acid solution of 8-hydroxyquinoline with iodine trichloride. Attempted reaction of 4,7-dihydroxy-10-chloro-dibenzo $[b, h]$ [1,6] naphthyridine (IV) with iodine trichloride failed because of the insoluble nature of the compound. On the other hand ready acid labile nature of 7-amino compounds put limitations in carrying out reactions on such substrates. Our preliminary attempts to effect iodochlorination below 0° produced a compound which soon transformed into an intractable pasty mass.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Hydroxy-7-(4-diethylamino-1-methylbutylamino)10-chlorodibenzo [b, h] [1, 6] naphthyridine (IIIa): A mixture of freshly distilled phenol (15 g) and 2-amino-5-diethylaminopentane (3.75 g) was kept under vacuum at 100° for 2 hrs. Freshly dried 4-hydroxy-7,10-dichloro dibenzo $[b, h]$ [1, 6] naphthyridine (II) (2.4 g, 0.076 mole) was added to the mixture

4. J. H. Burekhalter, F. H. Tendick, E. M. Jones, P. A. Jones, W. F. Holcomb and A. L. Rawlins, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1363.

and then heated on a steambath when a dark red colour slowly developed. After 4 hrs. the solution was cooled and poured into cold aq. sodium hydroxide (100 ml, 1*N*), the oily suspension was extracted immediately with ether (2×25 ml.). The base was further purified by extraction of the ethereal solution with acetic acid (1*N*, 100 ml), basification with ammonia (aq.) and re-extracted with ether (2×25 ml.). The ethereal solution was then dried (anhyd. K₂CO₃). Evaporation of the solvent afforded a semisolid mass which was dissolved in petroleum ether (40–60°) (25 ml) and cooled. 4-Hydroxy-7-(4-diethylamino-1-methylbutylamino)-10-chlorodibenzo [*b*, *h*] [1, 6] naphthyridine (IIIa) (3.0 g) separated as a low melting solid. This was dissolved in dry ethanol, treated with ethanolic hydrochloric acid (congo red) at 0–5°, diluted with dry ether to turbidity and chilled. The hydrochloride of 4-hydroxy-7-(4-diethylamino-1-methylbutylamino)-10-chlorodibenzo [*b*, *h*] [1, 6] naphthyridine (3.0 g) separated out as brownish red crystals. For an analytical sample the hydrochloride was dissolved in dry ethanol (0–5°), made turbid with dry ether and chilled; the solid was collected and dried, m.p. 195–200° (dec.). Found : C, 55.3; H, 6.25; Cl, 25.8; Calc. for C₂₅H₂₉OCl.N₄, 3HCl : C, 54.95; H, 5.86; Cl, 26.00%.

*Action of 1 : 1 aqueous hydrochloric acid on 4-hydroxy-7-(4-diethyl-amino 1-methylbutyl-amino)-10-chlorodibenzo [*b*, *h*] [1, 6] naphthyridine (IIIa) :* The clear solution formed by dissolving the compound (IIIa) (0.05 g) in 1 : 1 hydrochloric acid (5 ml) was allowed to stand at room temperature (25–30°) for 20 hrs. During this time a crystalline hydrochloride was formed. The product was collected, triturated with aq. ammonia and crystallised two times from ethanol, m.p. 295–298°. Mixed melting point determination with 4,7-dihydroxy-10-chlorodibenzo [*b*, *h*] [1, 6] naphthyridine (IV) showed no depression. The infra-red spectra of the two samples were found to be superimposable.

The separated hydrochloride on crystallisation from ethanol gave white crystalline solid, which turns yellow when dried on a steam bath, m.p. > 360°. Found : C, 58.05; H, 3.41; Calc. for C₁₆H₉ClO₂N₂, HCl : C, 57.66; H, 3.0%.

*4-Hydroxy-7-(4-methoxyanilino)-10-chlorodibenzo [*b*, *h*] [1, 6] naphthyridine (IIIb) :* To a solution of 4-hydroxy-7,10-dichlorodibenzo [*b*, *h*] [1, 6] naphthyridine (II) (0.315 g, 0.001 mole) in dry toluene (10 ml), *p*-anisidine (0.123 g, 0.001 mole), dissolved in toluene (5 ml), was added. The reaction mixture was heated under gentle reflux for 2 hrs.; deep red crystals slowly formed during this time. The solid was separated from the cooled mixture, triturated with aq. ammonia, collected, washed with water and dried (yield : 0.30 g, 77%). After several crystallisations from ethanol, the compound melted at 156–158°; λ_{max}^{EtOH} 270 m μ (ϵ 67200). Found : C, 69.08; H, 4.26; Calc. for C₂₃H₁₆Cl.N₃O₂ : C, 68.74; H, 3.98%

*4-Hydroxy-7-(4-hydroxyanilino)-10-chlorodibenzo [*b*, *h*] [1, 6] naphthyridine (IIIc) :* This compound was prepared from 4-hydroxy 7,10-dichloro dibenzo [*b*, *h*] [1, 6] naphthyridine (0.315 g, 0.001 mole) and *p*-aminophenol (0.109 g, 0.001 mole) essentially as described above in the preparation of the corresponding methoxy derivative (IIIb). The compound was obtained as deep red needles on crystallisation from ethanol; m.p. 245–250°, yield, 0.25 g (64.5%). Found : C, 68.40; H, 4.00; Calc. for C₂₂H₁₄Cl N₃O₂ : C, 68.13; H, 3.61%.

Attempted Mannich reaction on 4,7-dihydroxy-10-chlorodibenzo [b, h] [1, 6] naphthyridine : A solution of 4, 7-dihydroxy-10-chlorodibenzo [b, h] [1, 6] naphthyridine (0.593 g, 0.002 mole), diethylamine (0.146 g., 0.002 mole) and paraformaldehyde (0.1 g., 0.003 mole) in ethanol (30 ml.) was heated under reflux for 6 hrs. The solution was filtered hot and the filtrate concentrated and cooled. The dihydroxy compound was recovered unchanged.

The above reaction was carried out with diethylamine hydrochloride instead of the free base. The same results were obtained.

Attempted Mannich reaction on 4-hydroxy-7-(4-hydroxyanilino)-10-chlorodibenzo [b, h] [1, 6] naphthyridine (IIIc) : This compound (IIIc) was treated similarly as described in the case with 4,7-dihydroxy-10-chlorodibenzo [b, h] [1, 6] naphthyridine. The starting material was recovered unchanged.

4-Hydroxy-7-(4-hydroxy-3-diethylaminomethyl-anilino)-10-chlorodibenzo [b, h] [1, 6] naphthyridine (IIIId) : A solution of 2-diethylaminomethyl-4-acetamidophenol (0.354 g, 0.0015 mole) in 2 ml of hydrochloric acid (1 : 1) was heated under reflux for 1 hr. The cooled solution was basified with ammonia and immediately extracted with toluene (5 × 3 ml) and dried (Na₂SO₄). To this was added a solution of 4-hydroxy-7,10-dichlorodibenzo [b, h] [1, 6] naphthyridine (0.315 g, 0.001 mole) in dry toluene (10 ml), the mixture was heated on a steam bath for 2 hrs. and concentrated to 10 ml. The crystals which separated were collected, washed with a little ether and dried. This was suspended in chloroform and basified with ammonia in slight excess, the chloroform layer was separated, dried (Na₂SO₄) and the solvent removed. The title compound was crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 226–228°, yield 0.12 g (25%). Found : C, 68.85; H, 5.50; Calc. for C₂₇H₂₅Cl N₄O₂: C, 68.57; H, 5.29%.

Attempted iodochlorination of 4-hydroxy-7-(4-diethylamino-1-methylbutylamino)-10-chlorodibenzo [b, h] [1, 6] naphthyridine (IIIa) : This compound (IIIa) (0.87 g, 0.002 mole) was dissolved in conc. hydrochloric acid (5 ml.) by stirring the mixture below 0°. A solution of iodine trichloride in conc. hydrochloric acid (3 ml; 15%) was added dropwise with stirring to the above freshly prepared solution below 0° when a crystalline solid readily separated out. After keeping at that temperature for 15 mins, this was filtered. The yellowish solid slowly changed its colour to brick red and transformed into an intractible pasty mass.